

DEVELOPMENT OF POLITICAL RELATIONS BETWEEN THE COUNTRIES OF UZBEKISTAN AND TURKMENISTAN DURING INDEPENDENCE YEARS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8412614>

Abstract

The Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have lived with common goals as close friends, friendly neighbors, and strategic partners since time immemorial. Therefore, the roots of the relations between the two countries go back to a long history and are built on the basis of mutual respect and trust. Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have been drinking water from the same river for a long time and lived peacefully and harmoniously. Our peoples are united by a common history, common culture and values, similar language and customs. This closeness is the basis of strong cooperation between our countries.

Keywords

Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, neighbour, region, cooperation, Central Asia, political, history.

Introduction

The issue of mutual cooperation of states remains relevant in all eras, especially in modern geopolitical processes. interstate cooperation is one of the basic principles of international law, and its normative essence is that the goal of solving common global problems is the obligation of states to cooperate. In this regard, President Sh. Mirziyoev makes the following points. "Feeling responsibility for the common future of Central Asian countries is a solid foundation and guarantee of sustainable development and prosperity of the region." It is to turn Central Asia into a stable developed and highly developed region.

Contracts and Results

Such initiatives of the new leadership of Uzbekistan are important in ensuring peace and stability in the region, and in the development of bilateral and multilateral cooperation. In the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, priority is given to "advancement of bilateral and multilateral initiatives, including initiatives on expanding mutual cooperation, ensuring regional security and stability. directions are set. turning Central Asia into a region of peace, sustainable development and good neighborliness was defined by President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev as a priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy. this is reflected in the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of

development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. In particular, the Agreement on confidence measures in the border areas with Kyrgyzstan (2017), the Agreement on Strategic Partnership with Turkmenistan (2017), the state agreement of the three countries between the Republics of Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan about the point where the borders meet. The contract (2017) was signed.

In general, since 1991, relations between Central Asian countries have been developing in the spirit of close neighborhood and strategic partnership. This cooperation is based on long-standing fraternal ties, common history, language, religion and culture. In addition, a solid legal basis for interstate cooperation has been created. For example, Uzbekistan signed Strategic Partnership Agreements with the neighboring countries of Kazakhstan (2013, 2017), Turkmenistan (2017), Tajikistan (2018) and Kyrgyzstan (2019).

It is worth noting that the political and legal basis of the cooperation of sister countries began to be formed on the eve of independence. On April 19-21, 1991, a state delegation led by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov visited Turkmenistan, two republics. As a result of the signing of the Treaty on friendship and cooperation between the governments of the republics and the Agreement on economic and cultural cooperation between the governments of the republics in 1992-1995, the legal basis of cooperation between the two countries was created.

Between the governments of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan on April 14, 1993, on the basic principles of relations in the field of transport and communication, on August 28, 1993, on the basis of customs relations, and on October 11, 1993, on electronic mail communications signing of agreements along with the formation of the legal basis of interstate relations, it was reflected in practice as the legal basis of a number of documents signed in recent years. Because the political legal framework is the driving mechanism of any interstate cooperation.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid a state visit to Turkmenistan on March 6-7, 2017 at the invitation of the President of Turkmenistan Gurbanguly Berdimuhammedov. On April 23-24, 2018, the President of Turkmenistan Gurbanguly Berdimuhamedov visited Uzbekistan. 17 documents signed during his state visit serve to further develop friendly relations in the interests of the peoples of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev took part in the next meeting of the Council of Heads of State of the Commonwealth of

Independent States held on October 10-11, 2019 in Ashgabat, the capital of Turkmenistan. At the event, it was agreed to further develop cooperation in the fields of education, science, health care, culture, information, sports and tourism within the framework of the Commonwealth of Nations, which will help raise the level of culture and well-being of the citizens of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan within the framework of the CIS will give.

Uzbekistan's cooperation with the countries of Central Asia during 1991-2019 can be divided into three periods: the initial period, which includes the years 1991-2000, is a clear manifestation of the initiative of the First President I.A. Karimov, a number of intergovernmental agreements and agreements. It is determined by features such as the signing, holding of high-level meetings, promotion of the idea of "Turkestan - our common home". and the following years 2001-2016 were a period of relative decline in active relations, including water and electricity between the states of the region, border problems, lack of political will and the ability to transfer part of their sovereignty to a newly created political body, the state of their superiors factors such as personal ambitions, interference of external forces trying to take the region under their sphere of influence. at the same time, this period did not end only with the weakening of mutual cooperation, of course. Therefore, it is observed that the regional cooperation did not go smoothly during this period. The last third stage is marked by 2017-2019 and can be called a new stage of increased activity. Currently, Uzbekistan is conducting an active and pragmatic foreign policy based on the principles of close neighborliness and friendship with the countries of Central Asia. Especially in the last three years, there have been serious changes of historical importance in the development of cooperation in the region.

Conclusion

On the whole, these two countries, which have been playing the role of leaders in Central Asia, are taking big steps on their way. Both countries have their own interests in working together on this path. Both countries are interested in cooperation in the economic and political spheres, especially in the sphere of trade, cultural and other spheres. The heads of state firmly strove to develop and expand a large-scale strategic partnership, to enrich it with qualitatively new content, to achieve clear and effective results in the direction of the development and prosperity of our brotherly countries and peoples, and this has its positive results gave.

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